

inspire
SMART VILLAGE LABS

D6.3 INSPIRE Website

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

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Executive Summary

The present report is prepared as deliverable **D6.3 INSPIRE Website** of the INSPIRE project (Grant Agreement No. 101136592), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe. It introduces the INSPIRE project website structure and content, as this was created and developed within the first months of the project.

INSPIRE aims to support the sustainable and inclusive development of European rural areas by promoting social well-being and inclusion of rural dwellers and groups in a vulnerable situation and enhancing governance frameworks in rural areas. In particular, the project contributes to advancing in a multi-dimensional way the concept of social inclusion in rural areas, and supports access to high-quality social services by rural citizens through a series of awareness-raising, capacity-building, and pilot deployment activities that focus on social entrepreneurship and improvement of social services in a set of seven (7) different pilot territories (e.g., coastal, rural, peri-urban, mountainous). To realise its objectives, the project provides a novel territorial typology of rural areas, sets up and operationalises "Smart Village labs" in the selected pilot areas, and enhances governance frameworks and informed policy-making through E-Democracy and user-innovation techniques, to eventually deliver a dedicated Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard.

The project has selected a variety of communication channels (official website, social media, newsletter etc.) in order to disseminate its main objectives, activities, events, and primarily its achievements and results. Among these channels, the website is the focal point aggregating all communication efforts and acts as a point of reference. In this direction, the deliverable is organised into four main sections. It starts by introducing the current report and proceeds by describing the project's website and linked social media accounts, before ultimately concluding with the deductions resulting from the elaboration of the report. As the project evolves and various components and activities are materialised (Smart Village Labs, Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard, Capacity Building Programmes etc.) the website will be further enriched and developed accordingly to reflect project progress and act as one of the main communication and dissemination channels as described in the Dissemination and Communication Plan.

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List of Terms and Definitions

Table 1: Terms and Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
AB	Advisory Board
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MOOCs	Massive Open Online Courses
NoI	Network of Interest
PAs	Practice Abstracts
SMA	Social Media Accounts
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

This report, **D6.3 INSPIRE Website**, constitutes a description of the INSPIRE website structure and content, presents the functionalities of the webpage and briefly outlines the project’s social media accounts. These will be optimised and enhanced with essential dissemination materials, which are expected to serve as a multiplier of the project’s main ambitions and objectives. The website design was based on the graphical identity to ensure a uniform and distinct presentation in all communications and activities. The project’s graphical identity was developed early on (M3) and was presented in the report, titled **D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan - First**.

Q-PLAN, as the dissemination leader of the project, is responsible for the design, operation, and maintenance of the project’s website. All partners are responsible for providing materials and updates to be included on the website throughout the lifespan of the project. More specifically the Task Leaders responsible will provide materials for the particular sections of the website in regular intervals as stated below: (i) WR for the subpage of the Advisory Board (AB); (ii) ERDN for the subpage of the Network of Interest (NoI); (iii) ERDN for the subpage of Synergies; (iv) WR for the subpage of the Follower cases; (v) for the Smart Village labs subpages: PEDAL for Kosice (Slovakia), ERDN for Lubelskie (Poland), Medina for Kythera (Greece) & Konitsa (Greece), L'ADAPT for Bourgogne (France), WHEEL for Eastern and Midland Regions (Ireland), ROM for Maramures and Suceava (Romania); (vi) SEERC for the page of the Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard, with the support of UB for the Territorial typology of European rural areas, ESN for the Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment and ERDN for the Policy recommendations; (vii) KOC for the page of the Training Modules (MOOCs); and (viii) RUG for the Infographics on the needs of rural areas, social inclusion drivers and barriers. The website will be maintained throughout the project’s lifecycle, starting at the end of March 2025 and lasting two years beyond completion.

Regarding the website design process, a proposed sitemap was initially shared with all partners, who subsequently provided their feedback. Q-PLAN incorporated the input received and proceeded with the development of the website accordingly. Furthermore, partners contributed content for specific subpages in this initial stage, as follows: Advisory Board and Follower cases (WR), Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard (SEERC), Training Modules (KOC), Network of Interest (ERDN), and Promotional Material (Q-PLAN).

With that in mind, the following table outlines communication channels that currently shape the project’s online presence.

Table 2: The INSPIRE’s main online communication channels

Channel	URL
Website	https://inspireprojecteu.eu/
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/inspire-project-eu/
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61569429994625
BlueSky	https://bsky.app/profile/inspireprojecteu.bsky.social
X	https://x.com/INSPIRE_EU1
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@INSPIREproject-eu

All the above-mentioned online communication channels are expected to contribute greatly to the dissemination of the project results and outcomes. Considering that, this report encompasses the following:

- **The Introduction** provides a brief description of the INSPIRE project's online presence and introduces its website together with the social media accounts that complement the project's online presence.
- **Chapter 2** describes the INSPIRE website structure and content in order to support all the necessary horizontal activities of the project.
- **Chapter 3** outlines the social media channels employed for efficient dissemination, awareness raising and communication in conjunction with the project's website.
- **The Conclusions** briefly present the main elements of the website and the next steps in the development of the structure and contents in relation to the project's online presence.

Finally, the ANNEX presents the INSPIRE Privacy Policy, including sections about the INSPIRE website Privacy Policy and the INSPIRE website Cookies Policy.

The **project's privacy policy is available online** (website footer) so that all visitors can thoroughly read it. This document **may also be found in D7.3 Data Management Plan**.

The INSPIRE website is committed to being transparent and to ensuring that the privacy of its visitors is respected and protected. A Privacy Policy according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) also applies to the project website and governs personal information and collection usage by the website only. The cookie policy will specifically allow people to decide not to be tracked, following the GDPR requirements. In particular, it explains what type of personal data the web-portal collects, how it uses them and stores them, and issues that relate to the rights of users, their security, as well as descriptions about Google analytics.

2. The INSPIRE website

The INSPIRE website is publicly available at <https://inspireprojecteu.eu/> since March 2025 (M6) and it was designed during the early stages of the project to support all the necessary horizontal activities of the project. At the end of the project, the website should reach more than **6,000 visitors (KPI)**. Taking this into consideration, the website will be monitored periodically to assess whether the project is on the right path or if increased efforts are needed.

In addition, the INSPIRE website has a responsive design to allow consistency between what a site shows on a desktop and what it shows on a handheld device (Mobiles, tablets, etc.). Its layout guarantees easy browsing through its web pages. More specifically, the layout consists of:

- The **header** section contains the project logo and its acronym, as well as the **main navigation menu**. It facilitates fast browsing between the different pages of the website.
- The **main content area**, the main part of every page, providing tailor-made information to the visitors.
- The **footer** containing social media links, the partners' logos, the structure of the website (sitemap), the link to the privacy and cookies policy and under this, the information about the project's funding by the European Union's Horizon Europe framework and the respective disclaimer as per contractual obligation.

Figure 1: The INSPIRE website header

Figure 2: The INSPIRE website footer

INSPIRE Privacy Policy

White Research SRL

JANUARY 2025

INSPIRE website Privacy Policy

INSPIRE project website: <https://inspireprojecteu.eu/>

At INSPIRE, we respect our visitors. This Privacy Policy is provided by INSPIRE and applies to all information collected by us.

If you have additional questions or comments, please contact us.

This Privacy Policy applies to all information collected by us.

Consent

By using our website, you consent to the use of cookies.

Information we collect

The personal information we collect includes:

If you contact us, we collect your name, address, phone number, and email address.

When you register, we collect your name, company name, and email address.

How we use your information

We use the information we collect to:

- Provide you with the services you request.

INSPIRE Privacy Policy

INSPIRE website Cookies Policy

This is the Cookie Policy for INSPIRE, accessible from <https://inspireprojecteu.eu/privacy-policy/>

What Are Cookies

As is common practice with almost all professional websites, this site uses cookies, which are tiny files that are downloaded to your computer, to improve your experience. This page describes what information they gather, how we use it and why we sometimes need to store these cookies. We will also share how you can prevent these cookies from being stored, however this may downgrade or 'break' certain elements of the site's functionality.

How We Use Cookies

We use cookies for a variety of reasons detailed below. Unfortunately, in most cases there are no industry standard options for disabling cookies without completely disabling the functionality and features they add to this site. It is recommended that you leave on all cookies if you are not sure whether you need them or not in case they are used to provide a service that you use.

Disabling Cookies

You can prevent the setting of cookies by adjusting the settings on your browser (see your browser Help for how to do this). Be aware that disabling cookies will affect the functionality of this and many other websites that you visit. Disabling cookies will usually result in also disabling certain functionality and features of this site. Therefore, it is recommended that you do not disable cookies.

The Cookies We Set

- **Email newsletters related cookies:** This site offers newsletter or email subscription services and cookies may be used to remember if you are already registered and whether to show certain notifications which might only be valid to subscribed/unsubscribed users.
- **Forms related cookies:** When you submit data by using a form such as the forms that are found on contact pages or comment forms, then cookies may be set to remember your user details for future correspondence.

Third Party Cookies

- In some special cases we also use cookies provided by trusted third parties. The following section details which third party cookies you might encounter through this site.
- This site uses Google Analytics which is one of the most widespread and trusted analytics solutions on the web for helping us to understand how you use the site and ways that we can improve your experience. These cookies may track things such as how long you spend on the site and the pages that you visit so we can continue to produce engaging content.
- For more information on Google Analytics cookies, see the official Google Analytics page.

INSPIRE Privacy Policy Document

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Figure 3: Excerpt from the INSPIRE privacy policy, including the Website and Cookies Policy

The content and structure of the INSPIRE website were organised and designed to showcase the project, in terms of goals, background, work plan, consortium partners, use cases as well as the presentation of news related to the INSPIRE project work. Site visits, statistics, and other information on visitors' views (e.g., number of pages per visit, time on site, most viewed pages, etc.) will be measured using Google Analytics and other tools, to which the website is registered since the first day of its operation. The following list presents the main pages of the website, which are further analysed in the following subpages:

- **Home:** The website's front page holds a header menu as is presented in Figure 1, graphics from the project's identity and its full title are depicted, along with a short summary of the INSPIRE project, and a form to subscribe to the project's newsletter. The main purpose of this page is to provide a project overview at a glance. At a later stage, the project promotional video, planned for M12, will be embedded on the page below the project's summary.

Figure 4: The INSPIRE website frontpage layout (top & centre)

- **About:** This page aims to present all the detailed information related to the project. More specifically, the subpages are presented below.
 - **Concept & objectives:** This subpage introduces the INSPIRE's overall concept as well as the cornerstone objectives that will define the outcomes of the project.
 - **Methodology:** This subpage presents INSPIRE's three methodology phases: (1) Research and mapping phase, (2) Co-creation and piloting phase, (3) Sustainability phase.
 - **Consortium partners:** The purpose of this subpage is to show the project's consortium partners and provide details for each partner's profile with links to their respective websites.

Figure 5: The INSPIRE website About page (selected subpages)

- **INSPIRE Community:**
 - **Advisory Board:** This subpage will include information about the six Advisory Board members, each representing a key stakeholder group of the project (marginalized group, local authority, academia, social economy, EU stakeholders, civil society).
 - **Network of Interest:** This subpage will include information about the project's interactive multi-actor Network of Interest involving policymakers, NGOs and vulnerable groups organisations and social enterprises. More information will be added as soon as engagement activities take place. The Network of Interest will be available by **May 2025** (M8).
 - **Synergies:** This subpage will present a list of initiatives and sister projects that INSPIRE will collaborate with, in blocks with logos, along with the links to their individual websites.
 - **Follower cases:** This subpage will include the follower cases, which will be local or regional authorities or civil society organisations that are located in four additional rural areas and will adopt the INSPIRE Replication Handbook toward the end of the project.
- **Smart Village Labs:** The main aim of this page is to demonstrate the seven Pilot cases that will be implemented in the context of the INSPIRE project. The Smart Village Labs are expected to be available by **March 2026** (M18). An interactive map enables the description of the respective Smart Village Lab. This includes the name of the pilot area, the pilot partner, the category of rural territory and the potentially targeted vulnerable groups.
 - **Kosice region, Slovakia:** As the Smart Village Labs get established, this subpage will include more information on Pilot 1.
 - **Lubelskie Province, Poland:** As the Smart Village Labs get established, this subpage will include more information on Pilot 2.
 - **Kythera Island, Greece:** As the Smart Village Labs get established, this subpage will include more information on Pilot 3.
 - **Konitsa municipality, Greece:** As the Smart Village Labs get established, this subpage will include more information on Pilot 4.
 - **Bourgogne Franche-Comté, France:** As the Smart Village Labs get established, this subpage will include more information on Pilot 5.
 - **Eastern & Midlands Region, Ireland:** As the Smart Village Labs get established, this subpage will include more information on Pilot 6.
 - **Suceava and Maramures, Romania:** As the Smart Village Labs get established, this subpage will include more information on Pilot 7.

Smart Village Labs

INSPIRE sets up Smart Village labs in seven pilot areas across rural Europe to:

- support social inclusion and participatory governance through E-Democracy tools, boosting participatory democracy, connecting all key stakeholders and empowering rural dwellers and vulnerable groups towards decision-making.
- offer EU-wide and localised capacity building for upskilling and empowerment of rural populations, supporting entrepreneurial initiatives developed in the framework of the project and assisting the labs' transition into full-fledged "Smart Villages" and the participatory and digital upgrade of the pilot areas governance frameworks.

Figure 6: The Smart Village Labs page

- **Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard:** This page includes the INSPIRE Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard (which will be available by **July 2027**, M34), a project outcome that provides insights on how multi-level governance frameworks and economic policy instruments can be improved towards the empowerment and inclusion of rural vulnerable groups, in line with the Smart Villages principles. The Dashboard will be the technical product of three pillars: (i) the Territorial typology of European rural areas (to be available by **September 2025**, M12), (ii) the Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment (to be available by **January 2026**, M16), and (iii) Policy recommendations that will reflect the results from INSPIRE's innovative pilot actions. Later in the project, dedicated subpages will be created for each pillar, including a link to access each component.

Figure 7: The Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard page

- Training Modules:** This page includes information about INSPIRE's capacity-building programmes. These Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) aim to bridge knowledge gaps, empower local communities, and promote sustainable social economy practices through high-quality digital education. The page presents the MOOCs' key activities, information about their access and availability, audience and expected impact. It finally includes a registration form for interested potential participants. According to the project planning, MOOCs are expected to be available by **July 2026 (M22)**.

Training Modules (capacity building programmes)

As part of the INSPIRE project's mission to enhance social inclusion and economic resilience in rural areas, we focus on the development of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs). These courses aim to bridge knowledge gaps, empower local communities, and promote sustainable social economy practices through high-quality digital education. Our objective: This initiative is dedicated to designing and delivering engaging MOOCs tailored to the needs and challenges of rural communities. By leveraging insights from earlier research and activities within the INSPIRE project, the course content will be informed by real-world data to meet the specific requirements of target audiences.

Key Activities

1. Curriculum Development

- Conducting a comprehensive needs assessment to identify knowledge gaps.
- Designing a structured curriculum aligned with social economy principles and rural community needs.

2. Content Creation

- Producing interactive learning materials, including video lectures, case studies, and quizzes.
- Incorporating active learning techniques to engage diverse learners.
- Integrating real-life success stories of rural social enterprises to inspire action.

3. Technology Integration

- Utilizing user-friendly platforms for seamless learning experiences.
- Implementing interactive tools such as H5P (HTML5 Package), SCORM (Sharable Content Object Reference Model), and XAPI (Experience API) for enhanced engagement.
- Ensuring accessibility through mobile-friendly formats and multilingual options.

4. Quality Assurance & Evaluation

- Conducting pilot testing with end-users for feedback and improvement.
- Implementing post-course evaluations to assess impact and iteratively refine content.

Access & Availability

Open Access: The courses will be freely available to all interested learners.

Launch Date: August 2026.

Long-Term Availability: The courses will remain accessible indefinitely beyond their launch.

Where to Access: To be announced after August 2026.

Who Will Benefit?

- Rural residents seeking to enhance their skills and economic opportunities.
- Social entrepreneurs looking for guidance on sustainable business models.
- Policymakers and NGOs interested in supporting inclusive rural development.
- Academic and research communities working on rural innovation.

Expected Impact

- Improved access to education for underserved communities.
- Stronger local economies through enhanced knowledge of social enterprise models.
- Greater digital inclusion, fostering long-term rural resilience.

By making high-quality education accessible, our goal is to contribute to stronger, connected, and more prosperous rural communities.

The training modules will be launched in August 2026!
 Leave us your email here and we will make sure you do not forget about it!

Figure 8: The Training Modules page

- **Resources/Outcomes:**

- **Deliverables:** *This subpage is coming soon¹.* It will contain a list of the public deliverables together with download links as soon as these are available.
- **Practice Abstracts:** *This subpage is coming soon¹.* It will contain **(1) “Practice Abstracts – batch 1”** on the (i) Territorial typology of EU rural areas and (ii) the Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment; and **(2) “Practice Abstracts – batch 2”** on the (i) Smart Village labs; (ii) the Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard; (iii) the Social economy solutions deployment roadmaps; and the (iv) Portfolio of INSPIRE innovative solutions.
- **Publications:** *This subpage is coming soon¹.* It will contain a list of the publications stemming from the scientific research conducted by the project partners in the framework of INSPIRE.
- **Promotional material:** List of the promotional material (project overview presentation, poster, leaflet and roll-up banner) developed to communicate the project and to support dissemination activities.
- **Infographics:** *This subpage is coming soon¹.* It will contain infographics depicting qualitative and quantitative data about the needs of rural areas, social inclusion drivers and barriers in national contexts.

- **News & Events:** This page gathers the news and events of the project. It will also provide access to the project’s newsletters.

- **News & Press Releases:** This subpage contains a list of news related to the goals of the project and the publication of project results. It will be used to share experiences and outcomes between the partners and the community of website users. Individual pages for each news item appear as soon as the images or hyperlinked headers of each news item block are clicked.

¹ Certain subpages will be available as soon as project activities allow meaningful content to be added to them. The unavailable subpages have their core structure defined, as indicated within the main text of the document.

Figure 9: The News & Press Releases subpage

- **Events:** *This subpage is coming soon².* It will contain a list of events related to the project to share more information about what was presented at each event.
- **Newsletters:** *This subpage is coming soon².* In this subpage, the website visitors will be able to see all the project newsletters as well as subscribe to the project’s newsletter in order to receive future editions via mail. The project’s newsletter will be distributed using the Mailchimp tool, as explained in “D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan - First”. The first newsletter will be released after the upcoming 2nd Project Meeting in Lublin, Poland in April 2025.
- **Contact us:** Through this page, website visitors are able to communicate with a representative of the project’s consortium by filling out their comments or inquiries through a dedicated form. Responding to inquiries and comments received via the contact form is primarily the responsibility of the project dissemination manager. In case a query concerns a specific project activity related to a partner’s work, then it is forwarded to the partner. In addition, the page contains details of key project focal points (Project Coordinator and Dissemination manager), a subscription form for the project’s Newsletter, as well as links to the project’s social media channels.

² Certain subpages will be available as soon as project activities allow meaningful content to be added to them. The unavailable subpages have their core structure defined, as indicated within the main text of the document.

[About](#) | [INSPIRE Community](#) | [Smart Village Labs](#) | [Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard](#) | [Training Modules](#) | [Resources](#) | [News & Events](#) | [Contact Us](#)

Your name

Your email

Subject

Your message (optional)

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Subscribe to our newsletter:

Your email address

give INSPIRE Project the consent to collect and process my data according to the [Privacy and Cookies Policy](#)*

Subscribe

PROJECT PARTNERS

	<p>About</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concept and Objectives Methodology Consortium Partners <p>INSPIRE Community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advisory Board Network o Interest Synergies Follower Cases 	<p>Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deliverables Practice Abstracts Publications Promotional Material Infographics <p>Smart Village Labs</p> <p>Training Modules</p>	<p>News & Events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> News & Press Releases Events Newsletters <p>Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard</p> <p>Privacy & Cookies Policy</p> <p>Contact Us</p>
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Figure 10: The Contact us page

3. INSPIRE’s presence on social media

Based on the social media networking trends, the presence of the project on major social media networks and content platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook, X has been delivered in M3 (also Bluesky in M5, and YouTube in M6). The project’s social media were first presented in **D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan - First**. To enhance the interlinkage of the website with the project’s social media accounts there are short links to all project social media channels on the INSPIRE website.

Figure 11: Social media links on the INSPIRE website

A quick overview of the main social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Bluesky and X) that have been created for disseminating the project results is presented below.

Figure 12: INSPIRE’s social media accounts

4. Conclusions and Next Steps

This report illustrated the **INSPIRE project website's structure and content**, that is the project's main online presence along with the Social Media Channels as part of a multi-dimensional dissemination and communication approach. This will address all relevant target groups and raise public awareness about the solutions to be created, developed and demonstrated in the framework of the INSPIRE project, paving the way for their successful rollout and uptake beyond the end of the project.

As the project evolves and various components and activities are materialised (Smart Village Labs, Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard, Capacity Building Programmes, etc.) the website will be **further enriched and developed accordingly** to reflect project progress and act as one of the **main communication and dissemination channels** as described in the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D6.1 – Dissemination and Communication Plan – First).

5. Annex – INSPIRE Privacy Policy

INSPIRE Privacy Policy

White Research SRL

JANUARY 2025

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1.0	29/11/2024	First version
1.1	10/12/2024	Reviewed by partners
2.0	18/12/2024	Version integrated in the DMP
3.0	31/01/2025	Final version based on comments by Ethics Mentor (contextual adaptations may be needed during project implementation on ad-hoc cases)

Disclaimer

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INSPIRE Privacy Policy

How we collect your personal data

We collect personal data both **directly** and **indirectly**:

Directly: We obtain personal data directly from individuals in a variety of ways, including but not limited to the following cases:

- an individual registers to attend in meetings and events we host and during attendance at such events;
- an individual participates in an interview or survey organised by us;
- an individual subscribes to our project newsletter;
- we establish cooperative relationships with an individual;
- we provide professional services pursuant to our contract with the European Commission.

Indirectly: We obtain personal data indirectly about individuals from a variety of sources, including:

- our research partners;
- our networks and contacts;
- public and open data sources such as public registers, news articles and internet searches;
- social and professional networking sites (e.g., LinkedIn).

What types of data we collect

We only collect the data that are necessary for the smooth implementation of our project. These data fall into the following categories:

- **contact details** (name/surname, e-mail address, phone number);
- **professional information** (job title, organisation, field of expertise);
- **demographics** (e.g. age, gender, nationality, income level);
- information about what a person **knows or believes regarding issues related to the project**;
- **videos and photos** (from people that attend our events).

Technical means of data collection

Your personal data may be collected via publicly available websites, via secure surveying software (e.g., Google Forms, EU Survey, SurveyMonkey) and via direct enquiry to you during project activities (e.g., participation in focus groups, face-to-face interviews, observational fieldwork). Should we collect your personal data in any other way than through direct inquiry with you, we will make sure to inform you about this and about the source of the data.

Bases of lawful processing

We process personal data on the following legal bases:

- **Legal obligations** - for processing activities required for compliance both with applicable national and European legislation as well as with the specific legal and regulatory framework of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union.
- **Consent** – for processing activities such as organisation of surveys, focus groups, and interviews, completion of questionnaires, and dissemination of project's results.
- **Contractual obligations** - for processing activities such as reporting to the European Commission and complying with project's publicity obligations.

What we do with your personal data

We process your personal data with the purpose of:

- Conducting research (e.g., interviews, focus groups, surveys);
- Disseminating our project's results to different types of stakeholders;
- Sending invitations and providing access to guests attending our events and webinars;
- Administering, maintaining, and ensuring the security of our information systems, applications, and websites;
- Processing online requests or queries, including responding to communications from individuals;
- Complying with contractual, legal, and regulatory obligations.

How we secure your personal data when process it

We apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threat your personal data. Based on the results of this risk assessment, we define and apply a set of both technical and organisational measures to mitigate the above security risks, including but not limited to:

- Data Protection Policies to guide our personnel when processing your data;
- Written contracts with organisations that process personal data on our behalf;
- Non-Disclosure Agreements with our personnel;
- Back up process, anti-malware protection, access control mechanisms, etc.

Do we share personal data with third parties?

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before we share the data. We may engage with several or all the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Google Drive, Dropbox, Microsoft SharePoint);
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;
- Dissemination services providers (e.g., Mailchimp);
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with applicable law or regulation;
- The European Commission, according to our relevant contractual obligations (e.g., Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement).

Do we transfer your personal data outside the European Economic Area?

We do not own file servers located outside the European Economic Area (EEA). However, some partners may use cloud and / or marketing services from reputable providers such as Google Drive, SharePoint, Dropbox, Mailchimp, etc., situated both inside and outside the EEA. We always check that such providers comply with the relevant GDPR requirements before starting using their services.

INSPIRE website Privacy Policy

INSPIRE project website: <https://inspireprojecteu.eu/>

At INSPIRE, accessible from <https://inspireprojecteu.eu/>, one of our main priorities is the privacy of our visitors. This Privacy Policy document contains types of information that is collected and recorded by INSPIRE and how we use it.

If you have additional questions or require more information about our Privacy Policy, do not hesitate to contact us.

This Privacy Policy applies only to our online activities and is valid for visitors to our website with regards to the information that they shared and/or collected in INSPIRE. This policy is not applicable to any information collected offline or via channels other than this website.

Consent

By using our website, you hereby consent to our Privacy Policy and agree to its terms.

Information we collect

The personal information that you are asked to provide, and the reasons why you are asked to provide it, will be made clear to you at the point we ask you to provide your personal information.

If you contact us directly, we may receive additional information about you such as your name, email address, phone number, the contents of the message and/or attachments you may send us, and any other information you may choose to provide.

When you register for an Account, we may ask for your contact information, including items such as name, company name, address, email address, and telephone number.

How we use your information

We use the information we collect in various ways, including to:

- Provide, operate, and maintain our website

- Improve, personalise, and expand our website
- Understand and analyse how you use our website
- Develop new products, services, features, and functionality
- Communicate with you, either directly or through one of our partners, including for customer service, to provide you with updates and other information relating to the website, and for marketing and promotional purposes
- Send you emails
- Find and prevent fraud

Log Files

INSPIRE follows a standard procedure of using log files. These files log visitors when they visit websites. All hosting companies do this as a part of hosting services' analytics. The information collected by log files include internet protocol (IP) addresses, browser type, Internet Service Provider (ISP), date and time stamp, referring/exit pages, and possibly the number of clicks. These are not linked to any information that is personally identifiable. The purpose of the information is for analysing trends, administering the site, tracking users' movement on the website, and gathering demographic information.

Cookies and Web Beacons

Like any other website, INSPIRE uses "cookies". These cookies are used to store information including visitors' preferences, and the pages on the website that the visitor accessed or visited. The information is used to optimise the users' experience by customising our web page content based on visitors' browser type and/or other information.

GDPR Data Protection Rights

We would like to make sure you are fully aware of all of your data protection rights. Every user is entitled to the following:

- The right to access – You have the right to request copies of your personal data. We may charge you a small fee for this service.
- The right to rectification – You have the right to request that we correct any information you believe is inaccurate. You also have the right to request that we complete the information you believe is incomplete.
- The right to erasure – You have the right to request that we erase your personal data, under certain conditions.
- The right to restrict processing – You have the right to request that we restrict the processing of your personal data, under certain conditions.
- The right to object to processing – You have the right to object to our processing of your personal data, under certain conditions.
- The right to data portability – You have the right to request that we transfer the data that we have collected to another organisation, or directly to you, under certain conditions.

If you make a request, we have one month to respond to you. If you would like to exercise any of these rights, please contact us.

Children's Information

Another part of our priority is adding protection for children while using the internet. We encourage parents and guardians to observe, participate in, and/or monitor and guide their online activity.

INSPIRE does not knowingly collect any Personal Identifiable Information from children under the age of 13. If you think that your child provided this kind of information on our website, we strongly encourage you to contact us immediately and we will do our best efforts to promptly remove such information from our records.

Changes to This Privacy Policy

We may update our Privacy Policy from time to time. Thus, we advise you to review the INSPIRE website page periodically for any changes. We will notify you of any changes by posting the new Privacy Policy on this page. These changes are effective immediately, after they are posted on this page.

Contact Us

If you have any questions or suggestions about our Privacy Policy, do not hesitate to contact us through INSPIRE website: <https://inspireprojecteu.eu/contact-us/>

INSPIRE website Cookies Policy

This is the Cookie Policy for INSPIRE, accessible from <https://inspireprojecteu.eu/privacy-policy/>

What Are Cookies

As is common practice with almost all professional websites, this site uses cookies, which are tiny files that are downloaded to your computer, to improve your experience. This page describes what information they gather, how we use it and why we sometimes need to store these cookies. We will also share how you can prevent these cookies from being stored, however this may downgrade or 'break' certain elements of the site's functionality.

How We Use Cookies

We use cookies for a variety of reasons detailed below. Unfortunately, in most cases there are no industry standard options for disabling cookies without completely disabling the functionality and features they add to this site. It is recommended that you leave on all cookies if you are not sure whether you need them or not in case they are used to provide a service that you use.

Disabling Cookies

You can prevent the setting of cookies by adjusting the settings on your browser (see your browser Help for how to do this). Be aware that disabling cookies will affect the functionality of this and many other websites that you visit. Disabling cookies will usually result in also disabling certain functionality and features of this site. Therefore, it is recommended that you do not disable cookies.

The Cookies We Set

- ❖ **Email newsletters related cookies:** This site offers newsletter or email subscription services and cookies may be used to remember if you are already registered and whether to show certain notifications which might only be valid to subscribed/unsubscribed users.
- ❖ **Forms related cookies:** When you submit data by using a form such as the forms that are found on contact pages or comment forms, then cookies may be set to remember your user details for future correspondence.

Third Party Cookies

- In some special cases we also use cookies provided by trusted third parties. The following section details which third party cookies you might encounter through this site.
- This site uses Google Analytics which is one of the most widespread and trusted analytics solutions on the web for helping us to understand how you use the site and ways that we can improve your experience. These cookies may track things such as how long you spend on the site and the pages that you visit so we can continue to produce engaging content.
- For more information on Google Analytics cookies, see the official Google Analytics page.

- Third party analytics are used to track and measure usage of this site so that we can continue to produce engaging content. These cookies may track things such as how long you spend on the site or pages you visit which helps us to understand how we can improve the site for you.
- From time to time, we test new features and make subtle changes to the way that the site is delivered. When we are still testing new features, these cookies may be used to ensure that you receive a consistent experience whilst on the site, also ensuring that we understand which optimisations our users appreciate the most.
- We also use social media buttons and/or plugins on this site that allow you to connect with your social network in various ways. For these to work, we will set cookies through our site which may be used to enhance your profile on their site or contribute to the data they hold for various purposes outlined in their respective privacy policies.

More Information

Hopefully that has clarified things for you and as was previously mentioned if there is something that you are not sure whether you need or not it is usually safer to leave cookies enabled in case it does interact with one of the features you use on our site.

For more general information on cookies, please read the [Cookies Policy article](#).

However, if you are still looking for more information, you can contact us through INSPIRE website: <https://inspireprojecteu.eu/contact-us/>

Your rights

You have the following rights regarding our processing of your personal data:

- **Right to withdraw consent** – You can withdraw consent that you have previously given to one or more specified purposes to process your personal data. This will not affect the lawfulness of any processing carried out before you withdraw your consent.
- **Right to access** – You can ask us to verify whether we are processing personal data about you and, if so, to have access to a copy of such data.
- **Right to rectification and erasure** – You can ask us to correct our records if you believe they contain incorrect or incomplete information about you or ask us to erase your personal data after you withdraw your consent to processing or when we no longer need it for the purpose it was originally collected.
- **Right to restriction of processing** – You can ask us to temporarily restrict our processing of your personal data if you contest the accuracy of your personal data, prefer to restrict its use rather than having us erase it, or need us to preserve it for you to establish, exercise or defend a legal claim. A temporary restriction may apply while verifying whether we have overriding legitimate grounds to process it. You can ask us to inform you before we lift that temporary processing restriction.
- **Right to data portability** – In some circumstances, where you have provided personal data to us, you can ask us to transmit that personal data (in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format) directly to another entity.
- **Right to object** – You can object to our use of your personal data for direct marketing purposes, including profiling or where processing has taken the form of automated decision-making. However, we may need to keep some minimal information (e.g., e-mail address) to comply with your request to cease marketing to you.
- **Right to make a complaint to your local Data Protection Authority (DPA)** regarding any concerns you may have about our data handling practices.

(see https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/structure/data-protection-authorities/index_en.htm)

To ask us to do anything of the above, you can contact us through INSPIRE website: <https://inspireprojecteu.eu/contact-us/>

Or at: tbakratsas@white-research.eu

We will promptly examine your request against the relevant requirements of the laws and regulations governing privacy and personal data protection and we will answer the latest within 30 days after receiving your request. We will ask from you some kind of identification (e.g., photocopy of your identity card or passport) to avoid non-authorized reveal of your personal data. If, for reasons of complexity of the request or a multitude of requests, we are unable to respond promptly, we will notify you within 30 days of any delay, which in no case may exceed two months from the expiration of the 30-day deadline.

How long do we retain personal data?

We retain personal data to provide our services, stay in contact with you and to comply with applicable laws, regulations, and contractual obligations to which we are subject. Please note that we have an obligation to retain data concerning projects funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union for up to five years after the end of the project (unless further retention is requested by auditors). After the expiry of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, we will dispose of personal data in a secure manner.

Disclaimer of liability for third party websites

Although our site may contain links to third-party sites, including the sites of the consortium partners, we are not responsible for the privacy practices or content of these sites, and we expressly disclaim any liability for any loss or damage that may be caused by the use of these links. We do not monitor the privacy practices or the content of these sites. If you have any questions about the privacy practices of another site, you should contact the site's responsible personnel. We suggest you read the privacy policy of each website you interact with, before allowing the collection and use of your personal data.

We may also provide social media features that allow you to share information on your social networks and interact with our project on various social media sites. The use of these social media features may result in the collection or sharing of information about you. We recommend that you check the privacy policies and regulations of the social networking sites you interact with, so that you can be sure that you understand what information may be collected, used, and disclosed by these sites.

inspire

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PARTNERS

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